

THE ESSENCE OF TEACHING FOLK INSTRUMENTS

***Abstract.** This article describes the history and improvement of folk instruments, the President's attention to art, decisions, the importance of music culture today, the place of Uzbek folk instruments in music, the study of folk instruments, and the content of teaching.*

***Keywords:** national, music, festival, folklore, musical instrument, art, performance, culture, international.*

Without developing the sense of beauty in a person's heart, it is impossible to talk about a spiritually perfect person. Therefore, music, which has a powerful power, covers the human heart with its charm and leads it to beauty. That is why it is not for nothing that music is called "the heart of the people, the nation".

Thanks to the great attention paid by President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev to the development of the sphere of culture and art, the national art of music began a new period of its development. As a practical result of these reforms, it is worth noting the large international festivals and competitions held in different regions of our Republic. In particular, the "International Status Conference" held in Shahrisabz, the "International Art of Giving" festivals held in Surkhandarya and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the "Great Silk Road" International Folklore Music Festival in Margilan, The organization of major cultural events, such as the "International Handicrafts" festival held in Kok, is an opportunity to present our national culture to the world community and exchange experience with them in the field of culture and art, to strengthen cultural and spiritual relations, to promote international cultural serves to expand relations and widely spread Uzbek national culture and art.

President Sh.M. According to the decision PQ-112 "On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art" signed by Mirziyoyev on February 2, 2022 - from the academic year 2022-2023 in educational institutions, a number of measures aimed at increasing the cultural knowledge and skills of pupils and students, love for national culture, identifying and supporting young talents are carried out [1]. In particular, schoolchildren are taught the skill of playing at least one of the national musical instruments, and a note about this is included in their educational document and certificate.

Music teachers have huge responsibilities. It is appropriate to use five activities when passing music culture lessons [2, 3]. These activities are: musical literacy, listening, singing as a group, performing rhythmic movements to music, and accompanying musical instruments. Music teachers must have the ability to

play at least one of the national instruments, and at least three from the 2023-2024 academic year [4,5].

They are allowed to take music lessons and conduct club activities while maintaining their salary at the main place of work. In the music classes, "instrument performance" classes are organized under the slogan "Instrument accompanies my life".

In general secondary educational institutions:

To this decision, the skill of playing tunes on at least one of the national musical instruments listed in Appendix 1 is taught, and a corresponding note is included in their educational document;

There is one study hour per week for music, and in addition, practical circles and optional lessons on playing tunes on national musical instruments are held every week.

In general secondary, secondary special, professional and higher educational institutions:

Lecture concerts will be held by the State Philharmonic of Uzbekistan and its regional departments in cooperation with other cultural institutions;

Lecture concerts are organized in educational and cultural institutions and consist of practical exercises aimed at improving the musical culture and literacy of pupils and students, expanding their aesthetic taste, worldview, and feeling music;

The head of the appropriate educational and cultural institution, district, city administration or other responsible organization and the general director of the Uzbekistan State Philharmonic draw up a certificate about the holding of lecture concerts.

General secondary educational institutions, children's music and art schools, cultural centers:

- In 2022-2024, 3 sets of national musical instruments will be provided in accordance with the plan and schedule specified in Appendix 1 to this decision;

- the costs of providing sets of national musical instruments are financed from the funds allocated in equal shares from the republican budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and relevant local budgets;

- collections of national musical instruments are centrally purchased by the regional departments of the Ministry of Culture and the Ministry of Public Education.

At the moment, special attention is being paid to providing the schools of our Republic with music collections and special musical literature. During 2022-2024, ten thousand three hundred schools, three hundred and twenty-three children's music schools, eight hundred and twenty-six cultural centers will be provided with three sets of seven types of national musical instruments. For this purpose, a total of two hundred and five billion soums will be allocated from the republican and local budgets in equal shares.

Also, in 2022, ninety-two billion soums were allocated for the organization of practical circles for students in the fields of national musical instruments, fine and applied arts, and handicrafts.

Musical instruments, sound amplifier devices, technical equipment, lights, special clothes that are not produced in Uzbekistan will be exempted from customs duty until January 25, 2025.

As long as a person cannot feel the beauty embodied in the external world that surrounds him, in the people he communicates with in the society he lives in, and in the examples of artistic creations that were formed historically and practiced in a certain period, he will never reach the level of a spiritually perfect human being. cannot rise. Music gives a person aesthetic pleasure and allows him to feel the beauty around him. Music is one of the powerful means of forming and educating these delicate feelings. Musical instruments are a tool that glorifies the spirituality of humanity in tunes, that is, a product of human creativity, and it is one of the main tools that express the socio-cultural life processes of every nation. The melodies emitted by the instruments are created based on the spirit of the people. The Uzbek people have a rich ancient musical heritage, in which the role of musical instruments is of particular importance. Our musical instruments are considered the material and cultural wealth of our people, and they play an important role in the understanding of our cultural history and the development of our national culture, like other areas. It is known from history that at one time the Great Silk Road connecting Western and Eastern countries passed through the territory of Uzbekistan, which caused the culture of other nations to enter our land and spread our culture to the culture of other nations. This, by itself, created the ground for the rise of all fields, especially the development of music culture, like other fields, and the preservation of many musical instruments in the territory of our country. Uzbek folk instruments have been developing over centuries in a form suitable for all branches of music in their own way.

Historical manuscripts list the names of all musical instruments used in the practice of the peoples of Central Asia. Musical brochures contain information about musical instruments. Among them are Borbad string instruments - oud, rud, kobiz, gijjak, navha, nuzkha, kanon, chang rubob, tanbur, dutor; from musical instruments - ruhafza, shammoma, organun, sibizga, nayi, anbon, chagana, bulamon, trumpet, flute, koshnay, trumpet; Various levels of information about musical instruments such as tambourine, circle, drum, safoil are given.

Musical instruments have also developed in line with the passage of time and social development, and have been improved and perfected in accordance with the times. Along with modern music, family examples of folk instruments such as chang, rubob, dutor, gijjak were created. Due to the modern process, various compositions of musical instruments suitable for different directions have appeared. Various types of traditional, reworked, improved, restored, new modern musical instruments are widely used in practice. In the process of improvement, the enrichment of the musical instruments' form and singing capabilities has

gained great importance. These two criteria served as the basis for defining the spiritual and material value of the instruments.

Formation of musical instrument performance skills.

Mastering the skill of playing an instrument first of all involves sitting correctly, holding the sound of the instrument correctly, mastering the culture of making sound, forming the performance movements correctly, and fully observing the rules of collective performance:

- during the performance, the body should be held in such a way that it is comfortable for all actions of the performer and looks beautiful;

- it is customary to sit in the middle of the seat without leaning on the backrest, the left legs of the musicians are placed in front and the right legs are placed behind;

- the correct position of the right hand, freedom of executive movements is achieved;

- the left hand should not squeeze the handle, the palm should not touch the handle, it should be free;

- it is necessary for the musicians to sit carefully when starting the tune, to start together with the leading musician or the *auftaki* of the circle;

- when completing the tune, it is necessary to pay attention to the completion of the whole ensemble in one breath according to the same circle method;

- in the performance of the ensemble, it is necessary to observe the culture of collective performance, to sit carefully during the performance, not only to control the sound of one's own voice, but also the general sound of the ensemble and, accordingly, the sound of one's own voice;

- choosing a comfortable and correct position for performance, keeping hands free, properly mastering the culture of sound production are part of the content of the general requirements for the performance of each song.

There are more than 30 types of national musical instruments used in performance practice in Uzbekistan. Among them, 18 musical instruments were created after the 1940s by professor A.I. These are musical instruments developed in collaboration with a group of experts and musicians led by Petrosyans, and are intended for use as soloists on concert stages, but also mainly in orchestras and polyphonic ensembles. It was created on the basis of enlarging or reducing the shape of pre-existing national musical instruments, and it was the experiments carried out to create that family of instruments, resulting in the *nay*, *chang*, *rubob*, *dutor*, g the family of *ijjak* instruments was born. Musical instruments included in the composition of traditional folk instruments: *tanbur*, *dutor*, *sato*, *rubob*, *oud*, *flute*, *sunray*, *koshnai*, *trumpet*, *gijjak*, *chang*, *law*, *circle*, *drum*. Words used in folk art include *chanqobiz*, *sibizgi*, *safoil*. Samples of reworked musical instruments - *rubob*, *gizjak*, *dutor* and *chang* words, reworked according to the criteria of soprano, alto, tenor, bass voices of music.

The performance of traditional instruments has been formed in the practice of folk performance since ancient times, and it has been a tradition to use it based on various forms and compositions. First of all, each of the traditional instruments has a high professional level of individuality. In the practice of folk performance, corresponding performance opportunities, conditions and methods of employment have arisen.

Trumpets, sunrays, drums and a group of drum and percussion instruments formed in performance practice since ancient times and became an active participant in all public events of our nation. Ensembles of traditional musical instruments were used based on their characteristics. In order to have a large-scale and large voice in the performance, a large ensemble of instruments was formed from all instruments.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be said that it is our duty to convey the essence of Uzbek national music and Uzbek folk instruments to the younger generation, and we must preserve our musical heritage. We should introduce our Uzbek music to the world by learning the folk instruments that are our national musical heritage, using the possibilities of our Uzbek national songs, and playing various pieces.

References:

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